

Uncovering the Mysteries of the Mumps Virus: A Thorough Examination of Discoveries, Obstacles, and Paths Ahead

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Abstract

Mumps virus remains a significant public health concern globally, with outbreaks occurring despite vaccination efforts. The mechanisms of action of these herbal remedies, such as antiviral effects and immunomodulation, are discussed to elucidate their potential efficacy in combating the Mumps virus. Clinical evidence from existing studies and trials is reviewed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of herbal treatments for Mumps. Safety considerations, including side effects, herb-drug interactions, and regulatory frameworks governing herbal medicines, are also addressed. This review paper aims to explore the potential of herbal remedies as alternative or complementary treatments for Mumps virus infection. We provide an overview of the historical use of herbal remedies for viral infections, including Mumps, highlighting key herbs with purported antiviral properties and importance of further investigation into herbal remedies for Mumps virus, offering insights into potential avenues for improving treatment efficacy and patient outcomes.

Keywords: Mumps virus. herbal remedies. antiviral activity. Immunomodulation. safety considerations

Introduction

The mumps virus, a highly contagious pathogen primarily affecting children and adolescents, continues to pose significant public health challenges despite the availability of vaccines. The mumps virus has a long history with cases dating back to ancient times. However, it wasn't until the mid-20th century that researchers successfully isolated and characterized the virus (Fig. 1). The development of the mumps vaccine in the 1960s marked a turning point in controlling the virus's spread, although sporadic outbreaks persist [1]. The virus likely originated in animals, particularly birds, before adapting to infect humans. Its spread accelerated with globalization and crowded living conditions. Mumps, caused by the Paramyxoviridae family virus, primarily affects the salivary glands, leading to parotitis [2,3]. Vaccination efforts, notably the MMR vaccine, have reduced mumps incidence, but outbreaks still occur, often due to waning immunity, vaccine hesitancy, or occasional vaccine failures [4]. Surveillance and research into genetic variability and vaccine effectiveness are crucial for controlling mumps. Mumps infection progresses through stages, with characteristic parotid gland swelling, fever, headache, and muscle aches [5]. Complications like orchitis, oophoritis, or meningitis can occur, particularly in post-pubertal individuals or those with weakened immune systems. Supportive care is typically sufficient for recovery, but vaccination remains essential for prevention. Diagnosing mumps involves clinical evaluation, laboratory tests (viral culture, PCR, serology), and epidemiological considerations [6]. Differential diagnosis is critical to distinguish mumps from similar conditions and guide appropriate management. While conventional medical approaches focus on supportive care and vaccination, some herbal remedies may offer adjunctive benefits. For example, herbal teas with anti-inflammatory properties could potentially alleviate symptoms like swelling and pain [7]. Preventing mumps relies on high vaccination coverage, timely boosters, and infection control measures during outbreaks. Continued research into mumps epidemiology, vaccine development, and alternative treatments like herbal medicine will enhance our understanding and management of this infectious disease. The mumps virus remains a significant public health concern despite vaccination efforts. Comprehensive approaches encompassing vaccination, accurate diagnosis, supportive care, and potential adjunctive herbal treatments are crucial for controlling mumps and minimizing its impact on individuals and communities. Ongoing research and global collaboration are essential in addressing the challenges posed by this contagious pathogen. This review provides a comprehensive overview of the virus, including its history, origin, epidemiology, clinical manifestations,

diagnosis, treatment with a focus on herbal remedies, prevention strategies, and recent research advancements.

Fig. 1 Evolutionary Timeline of the Mumps Virus

Pathogenesis of Mumps Virus

The mumps virus, scientifically known as the Rubulavirus genus, is a single-stranded RNA virus belonging to the Paramyxoviridae family. Its structure (Fig. 2) comprises a lipid envelope studded with glycoprotein spikes that facilitate viral entry into host cells [8,9,10]. The transmission of the mumps virus primarily occurs through respiratory droplets from infected individuals, making it highly contagious, especially in crowded settings such as schools and communities. Upon exposure, the virus targets the upper respiratory tract and replicates within the epithelial cells of the salivary glands, specifically the parotid glands. This localization leads to the characteristic swelling and inflammation of the parotid glands, known as parotitis, which is a hallmark clinical feature of mumps infection. However, the virus can also affect other organs and tissues, including the central nervous system, pancreas, testes, and ovaries, leading to a range of clinical manifestations and complications [11,12]. The clinical manifestations of mumps infection typically begin with nonspecific symptoms such as fever, headache, malaise, and loss of appetite. These initial symptoms are followed by the development of parotitis, characterized by bilateral swelling and tenderness of the parotid glands [13]. In some cases, mumps infection can progress to involve other organs, resulting

in complications such as meningitis, encephalitis, pancreatitis, orchitis (inflammation of the testes), oophoritis (inflammation of the ovaries), and even hearing loss [14].

Fig. 2 Structure elucidation of Mumps Virus

Epidemiology of Mumps in India

The surveillance and analysis of mumps outbreaks and cases play a crucial role in understanding the epidemiological patterns, identifying risk factors, and guiding preventive strategies. In October and November 2023, mumps outbreaks in Idukki and Palakad in Kerala, Sivagangai in Tamilnadu, Udipi in Karnataka, and Rajnandgaon in Chhattisgarh, served as poignant reminders of the challenges posed by this infectious disease [15]. As per Global Health Observatory (GHO) data repository, India reported 758 mumps cases in 2021 and 6 cases in 2022 [16], indicating a substantial burden of mumps, particularly affecting children.

Current approach to treating Mumps virus

The mumps virus primarily affects children, especially those who are not vaccinated or have incomplete vaccination against the virus. It is highly contagious and spreads through respiratory droplets from infected individuals, making children particularly susceptible in environments like schools, daycare centers, and communities. Mumps infection in children typically manifests with symptoms such as swollen and painful salivary glands (parotitis), fever, headache, muscle aches, fatigue, and loss of appetite. In some cases, mumps can lead

to complications like orchitis (inflammation of the testicles) in boys who have reached puberty, oophoritis (inflammation of the ovaries) in girls, meningitis, pancreatitis, and deafness. Vaccination, specifically the MMR (measles, mumps, and rubella) vaccine, is highly effective in preventing mumps virus infections. It is recommended that children receive two doses of the MMR vaccine, with the first dose administered at around 12 to 15 months of age and the second dose at 4 to 6 years of age [17,18]. Additionally, Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) like ibuprofen or acetaminophen are commonly used to reduce fever and relieve pain associated with mumps-induced parotitis. NSAIDs can help alleviate pain and reduce fever, but they do not target the underlying viral infection [19,20].

Emerging Technological Innovations in Mumps Virus

Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS)

The use of NGS in mumps virus research has significant implications for public health. By identifying genetic variations in the virus, researchers can better understand how it evolves and spreads, which is crucial for developing effective diagnostic tools, vaccines, and antiviral therapies. Additionally, NGS data can help predict potential challenges in controlling mumps outbreaks and inform proactive measures to prevent future infections. Overall, NGS represents a powerful tool in the study and control of the mumps virus, offering insights that can shape strategies for disease management and ultimately contribute to improved public health outcomes [21,22].

Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-PCR)

Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-PCR) stands out as a pioneering molecular technique that has revolutionized the field of virology and disease diagnosis, particularly in the context of mumps virus detection and characterization. This technology plays a pivotal role in swiftly identifying mumps virus RNA in clinical samples, thereby facilitating rapid and accurate diagnosis of mumps infections. Its sensitivity and specificity make it an invaluable tool for healthcare professionals and researchers alike in their efforts to combat mumps outbreaks effectively. One of the key strengths of RT-PCR lies in its versatility. Beyond mere detection, RT-PCR enables genotyping and strain characterization of the mumps virus. By analyzing the genetic makeup and variations within different mumps virus strains, researchers can gain crucial insights into viral evolution, transmission patterns, and potential impacts on vaccine efficacy. This detailed genomic information is instrumental

in guiding public health strategies, such as targeted vaccination campaigns and outbreak containment measures [23,24].

Virus-Like Particle (VLP) Vaccines

VLP (Virus-Like Particle) vaccines represent a cutting-edge advancement in vaccinology, designed to mimic the structure of the mumps virus without containing any genetic material. This innovative approach ensures safety, as VLP vaccines cannot cause infections or viral replication. Recent developments in VLP technology offer several advantages over traditional vaccines, including improved safety by eliminating the risk of disease from weakened viruses. They also promise enhanced efficacy by triggering a focused immune response, potentially providing long-lasting protection and reducing the need for frequent boosters. VLP vaccines are stable and easy to store, making them ideal for mass vaccination campaigns and resource-limited settings. Their design flexibility allows for targeting multiple virus strains and variants, contributing to broad-spectrum protection [25,26].

Mass Spectrometry-based Proteomics

The mumps virus, Mass Spectrometry-based Proteomics reveals insights into viral protein composition, including structural, enzymatic, and regulatory proteins. Additionally, it sheds light on host-virus interactions, elucidating molecular mechanisms, host immune responses, and identifying potential therapeutic targets. A key contribution of Mass Spectrometry-based Proteomics is in antiviral drug development. By identifying crucial viral proteins or host factors essential for viral propagation, this technology guides the rational design of antiviral therapies. Targeted inhibition of these proteins disrupts viral replication cycles, offering promising avenues for novel drug development [27]. Furthermore, Mass Spectrometry-based Proteomics helps characterize post-translational modifications (PTMs) on viral proteins, such as phosphorylation and glycosylation. Understanding these modifications enhances our grasp of viral pathogenesis and provides additional targets for therapeutic intervention, making this technology indispensable in advancing mumps virus research and control strategies [28].

Digital Epidemiology and Surveillance

Digital Epidemiology and Surveillance revolutionizes infectious disease control, particularly in managing mumps virus outbreaks. It employs digital tools like social media monitoring, internet search analysis, and mobile health apps to track, analyze, and respond to mumps threats effectively. These technologies enable real-time access to mumps-related data, aiding

in swift detection of discussions and trends. Utilizing natural language processing and machine learning, they identify potential cases or clusters for rapid response and containment. Internet search analysis tracks mumps-related queries for early warning signs, guiding targeted interventions. Mobile apps assist in data collection, symptom reporting, and communication, empowering individuals and gathering epidemiological insights. This integration ensures rapid outbreak detection, comprehensive understanding, targeted communication, and data-driven decision-making, optimizing response strategies and resource allocation during mumps outbreaks [29].

Virus Neutralization Assays

Virus Neutralization Assays are essential tools in combating the mumps virus, with plaque reduction neutralization assays (PRNAs) and microneutralization assays standing out as key methodologies. PRNAs evaluate the neutralizing capacity of antibodies against the virus by measuring plaque formation in cell cultures with patient sera, providing precise insights into neutralization activity. Microneutralization assays offer high-throughput screening capabilities and assess neutralization across multiple virus strains simultaneously, making them valuable in large-scale studies and vaccine efficacy trials. These assays contribute significantly to mumps virus research and control by understanding immune responses, identifying protection correlates, and assessing vaccine durability. They also help gauge community immunity levels, detect protection gaps, and inform targeted vaccination strategies. Additionally, Virus Neutralization Assays aid in vaccine and antiviral development by prioritizing promising candidates with robust neutralizing responses and identifying potent antiviral compounds during preclinical studies [30].

Nanotechnology-based treatments for mumps virus

Nanotechnology-based treatments for mumps virus infections represent a cutting-edge frontier in medical science, brimming with potential solutions shown in (Fig. 3). Though these treatments are currently in their nascent stages, the prospects they offer are significant. One avenue of exploration involves engineering nanoparticles to serve as carriers for antiviral agents, such as drugs or RNA interference molecules tailored to disrupt viral replication. These nanoparticles could be finely tuned to target mumps virus specifically, minimizing collateral damage to healthy cells [31]. Nanoparticle-based vaccines also show promise, offering improved stability and targeted delivery for enhanced immune responses, potentially leading to more robust and lasting protection against mumps virus transmission. Additionally,

nanotechnology's ability to modulate immune responses opens doors for novel strategies in combating viral infections. Nanoparticles loaded with immunomodulatory compounds could bolster both innate and adaptive immunity, potentially mitigating the severity of mumps virus infections [32]. Furthermore, leveraging nanocarriers for drug delivery enables precise targeting of affected tissues, optimizing therapeutic outcomes while reducing systemic side effects. Nanotechnology's diagnostic prowess is equally promising, with nanoparticle-based biosensors and imaging agents offering rapid and accurate detection of mumps virus infections. These tools could facilitate early treatment initiation and effective outbreak containment [33].

Fig. 3 Nanotechnology based treatments for mumps virus

Gene Editing

Gene editing technologies like CRISPR-Cas9 provide opportunities to manipulate and control the mumps virus genome, despite its RNA nature and rapid mutations. Although directly editing the virus is complex, gene editing shows promise in combating mumps infections and developing innovative vaccines. In research, gene editing enhances host cells' resistance to infection by modifying genes involved in viral processes. This can reduce viral replication and severity of mumps-related complications. Gene editing also aids in creating safer vaccine candidates by designing attenuated or synthetic virus versions that maintain immunogenicity without causing disease. Engineered delivery systems improve vaccine stability,

immunogenicity, and targeted delivery, potentially enhancing efficacy while reducing doses [34, 35].

Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence

Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are transforming epidemiology, especially in studying mumps outbreaks. These technologies analyze vast data, detect patterns, and predict outbreak dynamics accurately, aiding in understanding transmission, identifying risk factors, and optimizing interventions. ML and AI handle diverse data sources like demographics, clinical data, and genomic sequences, unveiling hidden patterns relevant to mumps outbreaks. They identify spatial and temporal trends, detect early outbreak signals, and forecast future dynamics precisely, enabling proactive measures and tailored interventions. Supervised learning techniques in ML pinpoint mumps transmission risk factors, such as age, vaccination status, and social interactions. This foresight guides timely preventive measures, vaccination campaigns, and public health responses. AI-driven pattern recognition algorithms enhance outbreak surveillance by detecting subtle patterns, identifying clusters, and integrating multiple data streams like social media and environmental monitoring [36].

Single-Cell Analysis

Single-Cell Analysis in mumps virus research provides detailed insights into immune responses at the cellular level. It uses sequencing and analysis to understand how the virus interacts with individual immune cells, aiding in developing new immunotherapies and vaccine enhancements. This method reveals the diversity of immune cell populations, identifies rare cell types, and uncovers gene expression profiles and communication networks crucial for understanding how the virus evades the immune system. This technique used to develop targeted immunotherapies and vaccines, improve vaccine effectiveness, and design personalized treatment approaches for mumps pathogens [37].

3D Cell Culture Models

3D Cell Culture Models represent a revolutionary approach in studying mumps virus dynamics, pathogenesis, and intervention efficacy. Unlike 2D cultures, techniques like organoids and microfluidic systems recreate complex tissue architecture and cellular interactions, vital for understanding virus-host interactions and assessing potential treatments. Organoids, resembling real tissues, offer a sophisticated platform to study mumps virus

infection. They mimic cellular diversity and organization, allowing researchers to explore how different cell types respond to the virus in organs like salivary glands or lymphoid tissues. This helps assess viral tropism, replication kinetics, cytopathic effects, and immune responses in a physiologically relevant setting. Microfluidic systems provide precise control over cellular environments, simulating *in vivo* conditions. They incorporate multiple cell types, create gradients, and mimic tissue structures, ideal for studying mumps virus pathogenesis. These systems investigate cell-cell interactions, tissue barriers, and immune responses affecting virus infection and immune evasion. 3D Cell Culture Models play a crucial role in drug discovery and vaccine development against mumps [38].

Traditional Herbal Remedies for Mumps Virus

Herbal remedies have been used for centuries in traditional medicine systems to treat various ailments, including viral infections like mumps. Several herbs have been studied for their potential efficacy against the mumps virus. Some herbal remedies have shown promising antiviral properties in preclinical studies and may offer potential benefits in mumps management. One commonly used herbal remedy for mumps is licorice root (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*). Licorice root contains compounds such as glycyrrhizin and flavonoids, which exhibit antiviral activity against a range of viruses, including respiratory viruses. Studies suggest that licorice root extracts may inhibit viral replication and reduce viral load, although further research is needed to determine its specific effects against the mumps virus [39]. Another herbal remedy with potential antiviral properties is astragalus (*Astragalus membranaceus*). Astragalus contains polysaccharides and flavonoids that possess immunomodulatory and antiviral activities. While research on astragalus specifically targeting the mumps virus is limited, its general antiviral effects make it a subject of interest for potential therapeutic use in viral infections [40]. Additionally, traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) formulations often include herbal combinations known as "anti-viral decoctions" or "fire-eliminating formulas," which are believed to have antiviral properties. These formulations may contain herbs such as *Forsythia suspensa*, *Lonicera japonica*, and *Isatis tinctoria*, among others [41]. Studies have demonstrated the antiviral effects of these herbs against various viruses, although their efficacy specifically against the mumps virus requires further investigation.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this review highlights the persistent challenges posed by the mumps virus, despite advancements in vaccination strategies. The exploration of herbal remedies as potential adjunctive therapies brings attention to their antiviral and immunomodulatory properties, although with the need for rigorous scientific validation through clinical trials. Safety considerations, regulatory frameworks, and the historical context of herbal medicine underscore the complexity of integrating these remedies into mainstream mumps management. The emergence of technological innovations, from next-generation sequencing to nanotechnology-based treatments, presents promising avenues for advancing mumps virus research, diagnosis, and control. Collaborative efforts in conducting well-designed clinical trials, identifying bioactive compounds, assessing safety profiles, and integrating evidence-based herbal medicine are essential for improving mumps treatment efficacy and patient outcomes. The multidisciplinary approach, encompassing research, healthcare, policy, and public awareness, to address the challenges posed by the mumps virus and enhance global public health resilience against infectious diseases.

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